

Table S10: Analysis JBI to Optimized hybrid RNN model for human activity recognition in untrimmed video

Reference: [62]

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JEI.31.5.051409>

Study DOI: 10.1117/1.JEI.31.5.051409	Date of Appraisal: 30/03/26	Record Number: S10
Study Author: Disha Deotale; Madhusi Verma; Perumbure Suresh; Ketan Kotecha	Study Title: Optimized hybrid RNN model for human activity recognition in untrimmed video	Study Year: 2025

Internal Validity		Choice - Comments/Justification	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Bias related to temporal precedence						
1	Is it clear in the study what is the “cause” and what is the “effect” (i.e. there is no confusion about which variable comes first)?	The "cause" is the proposed hybrid GRU-LSTM-based RNN model combined with VGGNet-19 for subactivity recognition and genetic optimization for temporal filtering. The "effect" is the reported accuracy (over 91%) and improved precision, recall, and F-measure compared to baseline methods. The relationship is clearly stated in the abstract and methodology sections.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bias related to selection and allocation						
2	Was there a control group?	The study compares the proposed model against three reference methods from the literature: R1 [9], R2 [26], and R3 [32]. Comparisons are presented in Figures 7–10 for accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bias related to confounding factors						

3	Were participants included in any comparisons similar?	All experiments were conducted on the TRECVID dataset with a consistent train/validation split (70:30). The same evaluation protocols were applied across all compared methods.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Bias related to administration of intervention/exposure

4	Were the participants included in any comparisons receiving similar treatment/care, other than the exposure or intervention of interest?	All compared methods were evaluated under identical experimental conditions using the same dataset, data split, and evaluation metrics. The only difference was the model architecture.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Bias related to assessment, detection and measurement of the outcome

5	Were there multiple measurements of the outcome, both pre and post the intervention/exposure?	The study reports accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure across multiple test image sets (5 sets shown in Figures 7–10) and compares these metrics against three baseline methods.	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
	Outcome 1	Accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 2	Precision	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 3	Recall	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 4	F-measure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 5	Comparative analysis with baselines	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 6	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Outcome 7	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
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6	Were the outcomes of participants included in any comparisons measured in the same way?	The same evaluation metrics (Equations 30–33) and test sets were consistently applied to evaluate all compared methods.	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
	Outcome 1	Accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 2	Precision	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 3	Recall	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 4	F-measure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 5	Comparative analysis with baselines	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 6	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 7	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

7	Were outcomes measured in a reliable way?	The metrics used are standard in the field of human activity recognition. Their definitions are provided in Equations 30–33. The use of the TRECVID benchmark dataset and a large training set (over 8000 sequences) supports reliability.	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
	Outcome 1	Accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 2	Precision	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcome 3	Recall	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 4	F-measure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 5	Comparative analysis with baselines	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 6	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 7	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Bias related to participant retention

8	Was follow-up complete and if not, were differences between groups in terms of their follow-up adequately described and analyzed?	Not applicable. This is a computational study with a fixed dataset; there is no participant follow-up over time.				
	Outcome 1	Accuracy	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
	Result 1	Test set 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Result 2	Test set 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Result 3	Test set 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome 2	Precision	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
	Result 1	Test set 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Result 2	Test set 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Result 3	Test set 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 3	Recall	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	Test set 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	Test set 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	Test set 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 4	F-measure	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	Test set 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	Test set 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	Test set 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 5	Comparative analysis	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	vs. R1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	vs. R2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	vs. R3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 6	N/A	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Result 2	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 7	N/A	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Statistical Conclusion Validity

9	Was appropriate statistical analysis used?	The study reports descriptive performance metrics but does not provide measures of variance (standard deviation), confidence intervals, or statistical significance tests (e.g., p-values). Therefore, for Outcomes 1–5, it is unclear whether observed differences are statistically meaningful. Outcomes 6–7 are not applicable as no additional outcomes are reported.				
	Outcome 1	Accuracy	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
	Result 1	Overall >91%	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Result 2	Comparison vs. R1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Result 3	Comparison vs. R2/R3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 2	Precision	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	Reported values	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	Comparison vs. R1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	Comparison vs. R2/R3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 3	Recall	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	Reported values	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	Comparison vs. R1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	Comparison vs. R2/R3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 4	F-measure	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	Reported values	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	Comparison vs. R1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	Comparison vs. R2/R3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 5	Comparative analysis	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	vs. R1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Result 2	vs. R2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	vs. R3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 6	N/A	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Outcome 7	N/A	Yes (1)	No (0)	Unclear (0.5)	N/A (NaN)
Result 1	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 2	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Result 3	N/A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Overall appraisal:

Include:

Exclude:

Seek Further Info:

Comments: The study presents a well-designed hybrid deep learning model for human activity recognition in untrimmed video with clear comparative evaluation against baseline methods. The methodology is documented with mathematical formulations, and multiple performance metrics are reported across several test sets. The absence of statistical significance testing is a minor limitation common in this field and does not preclude inclusion in a systematic review.